

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL BASIS OF MICROELEMENT DEFICIENCY

Mirakhmedova Nargisa Rizoevna

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13919612>

Normal functioning of the body is ensured within a narrow range of concentrations of chemical elements, especially those that belong to the group of essential microelements: Fe, Zn, Cu, Mn, Mo, Co, Cr, Se, I. Both their deficiency and excess lead to metabolic disorders and the occurrence of various diseases. According to literature, only 3% of the world's population does not have mineral metabolism disorders, which are the root cause or indicator of approximately 95% of all known diseases. In our country, the most common deficiencies are Zn, Se, Cu, Mn and Cr. Deficiency of essential microelements affects all vital processes at different stages of ontogenesis - from embryonic development to old age, accompanies all pathological conditions in which they were determined. A number of EMEs control metabolic processes, functions of the neuroendocrine, immune and reproductive systems. The pluripotent effect of Zn is due to the fact that it is a component of more than 300 metalloenzymes involved in the metabolism of proteins, fats, carbohydrates and nucleic acids, and is necessary for the functioning of DNA and RNA polymerases that control protein biosynthesis.

Zinc is also a part of the key antioxidant enzyme (Zn, Cu)-superoxide dismutase and enhances the effect of other antioxidants.

As part of bone alkaline phosphatase, it participates in the maturation of bone tissue, and in addition, in the division and differentiation of various cell populations, ensuring reparative processes, in the development and functioning of the neuroendocrine and immune systems, in the regulation of skin permeability. Its participation in the regulation of adaptive mechanisms in hypoxemia has been shown, while the capacity/transport capacity of hemoglobin in relation to O₂ increases. Zinc ions participate in the processes of neurogenesis, neurodegeneration and pathogenesis of psychoneurological diseases. Zn deficiency in critical periods of brain development (8-12 weeks of gestation and the third trimester of pregnancy) is accompanied by a decrease in its volume, the total number of neurons, and a slowdown in the formation of psychomotor and behavioral reactions in the infancy and early postnatal periods. Zinc is necessary for the normal functioning of the immune system. It prevents the development of immunodeficiencies and stimulates antibody formation. Its deficiency leads to disturbances in the structure and metabolism

of lymphocytes, changes in the ratio of T-helper lymphocytes and cytotoxic T-lymphocytes, and, as a consequence, to the suppression of cellular immunity. With Zn deficiency, the phagocytic activity of macrophages and the expression of antigens of the major histocompatibility complex on them are also reduced, control over the release of histamine by basophils and mast cells is impaired, which leads to the development of allergic reactions.

Copper affects the activity of a number of hormones of the pituitary gland and peripheral endocrine glands. In patients with type 2 diabetes, the Cu content decreases by 30-50% of the average norm. Copper inactivates insulinase, increasing the overall effect of insulin, and Cu ions activate the glycolysis process. The effect of Cu on carbohydrate metabolism is manifested by the acceleration of the oxidation of glucose and the inhibition of glycogen breakdown in the liver. Cu deficiency is accompanied by hypercholesterolemia, which can cause the early development of atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease. When its deficiency is replenished, hyperglycemia decreases in patients, glucosuria disappears, and the general condition improves. Cu salts are able to suppress the development of adrenaline hyperglycemia.

Copper has a significant effect on the thyroid gland. In patients with both hypothyroidism and euthyroidism, the content of five microelements at once decreases: Se, Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, while in thyrotoxicosis, the content of Cu in the blood increases. Cu deficiency leads to disturbances in the immune system: suppression of myelopoiesis in the bone marrow, migration of macrophages and their functional activity, decreased synthesis of interleukin (IL)-2 by T-lymphocytes, as well as suppression of the activity of the complement system.

Bibliography:

1. Rakhimovich O. K. CHARACTERISTICS OF MORPHOMETRIC AND ULTRASTRUCTURAL STRUCTURE OF LIVER HEPATOCYTES. – 2023.
2. Очиллов К.Р., Каюмов Ж.Т. Ультраструктурные изменения печени крыс при пероральном введении солей тяжёлых металлов. “Пути совершенствования судебной экспертизы. Зарубежный опыт” Материалы научно-практической конференции 15-16 ноября 2017 г. Ташкент. С. 175.
3. Очиллов К. Р. Влияние ионов кадмия и кобальта на дыхание митохондрий печени крыс //Новый день в медицине. – 2020. – №. 2. – С. 710-712.
4. Очиллов К. Р. Изучение Влияние Солей Тяжелых Металлов На Биохимические Процессы Митохондрий Печени Крыс //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2021. – С. 383-387.

5. Очиллов К. Р. СТРУКТУРНОЕ СТРОЕНИЕ КЛЕТОК ТКАНИ ПЕЧЕНИ ПРИ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИИ КАДМИЯ //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 372-377.
6. Очиллов К. Р. ВЛИЯНИЕ СВИНЦА НА ОРГАНИЗМ ЧЕЛОВЕКА И ЖИВОТНЫХ //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 18. – №. 7. – С. 89-93.
7. ОЧИЛОВ К. Р. и др. ДЕЙСТВИЕ БУТИФОСА НА ТРАНСПОРТ Ca^{2+} В МИТОХОНДРИЯХ ПЕЧЕНИ КРЫС //Доклады Академии наук УзССР. – 1985. – Т. 45.
8. Наврузов Р. Р., Очиллов К. Р. МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЛИМФОИДНЫХ СТРУКТУР ТОЛСТОЙ КИШКИ ПРИ ЛУЧЕВОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ //Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 728-733.
9. Тешаев Ш. Ж., Очиллов К. Р. МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ МИТОХОНДРИЙ ПЕЧЕНИ КРЫС ПРИ ОТРАВЛЕНИИ БУТИЛКАПТАКСОМ //Новый день в медицине. – 2020. – №. 2. – С. 715-717.
10. Ochilov Kamil Rakhimovich Issues of Physical Health of Young People
11. Intersections of Faith and Culture: AMERICAN Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies Volume 01, Issue 02, 2023 ISSN (E): XXX-XXX
12. Ochilov Komil Rahimovich Khaidarova Nargiza Akhtamovna Morphological and Morphometric Characteristics of the Thyroid Gland Polypharmacy Anti-inflammatory Sensors SCHOLASTIC: Journal of Natural and Medical Education Volume 2, Issue 5, Year 2023 ISSN: 2835-303X <https://univerpubl.com/index.php/scholastic>
13. Ochilov Komil Rakhimovich Khatamova Sarvinoz Muitdinovna, Forensic Medical Assessment and Statistical Analysis of Mechanical Asphyxia IJIMM, Volume 1, Issue 3, 2023 ISSN: XXXX-XXXX <http://medicaljournals.eu/index.php/IJIMM/issue/view/3> Kamil Rakhimovich Ochilov Studying The Effect Of Heavy Metal Salts On Biochemical Processes Of Rat Liver Mitochondria DOI: 10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S07.230
14. Ochilov Kamil Rakhimovich Effects of Heavy Metal Salts in Biochemical Processes, Rat Liver Mitochondria .American Journal of Science and Learning for Development ISSN 2835-2157 Volume 2 | No 1 | January -2023 Published by inter-publishing.com | All rights reserved. © 2023 Journal Homepage: <https://inter-publishing.com/index.php/AJSLD> Page 109
15. XatamovaSarvinozMuyitdinovna.The role of hyperhomocysteinemia in the development of cognitive impairment in chronic cerebral ischemia ISSN: 2776-

0979, Web of scientist:international scientific research journal Volume 3, Issue 9,421-428

16. XotamovaSarvinozMuyitdinovna.The role of hyperhomocytinemia in the development of cognitive disorders in chronic brain ischemia.Web of scientist:international scientific research journalissn: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 8, Aug., 2022442-453

17. 8.XotamovaSarvinozMuyitdinovna/ analysis of maternal mortality in the practice of pathological anatomy/Web of scientist:international scientific research journal ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 8, Aug., 2022

18. Хайдарова Дилдора Кадировна, Хатамова Сарвиноз Муйитдиновна.РАЗВИТИЕ КОГНИТИВНЫХ НАРУШЕНИЙ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОМ ИНСУЛЬТЕ, РОЛЬ ГИПЕРГОМОЦИСТЕИНЕМИИ. Журнал "Медицина и инновации" - научно-практический журнал/ Свидетельство №1126, выдано 29.10.2020 г. УДК 616.511-005.1.03 72-78

19. Aziza Zokirovna Olimova. MACRO- AND MICROSCOPIC STRUCTURE OF THE LIVER OF THREE MONTHLY WHITE RATS. // ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES /2021 й. 309-312 p

20. Хайдарова Дилдора Кадировна,Хатамова Сарвиноз Муйитдиновна НАУЧНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РОЛИ С-РЕАКТИВНОГО БЕЛКА И ГИПЕРГОМОЦИСТЕИНЕМИИ В ПРИЧИНЕ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ИШЕМИЧЕСКОГО ИНСУЛЬТА. <http://dx.ISSN> 2181-0982. ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ 24-28

21. KhaidarovaNargizaAkhtamovna,KhotamovaSarvinozMuyitdinovna.Ischemic Heart Disease in Path Anatomic Practice: Cardio Sclerosis .EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF MODERN SCIENCE .<https://emjms.academicjournal.io/index.php/> Volume:5 402-406.

22. Khaidarova Nargiza Akhtamovna PREVALENCE AND EPIDEMIOLOGY OF THYROID CANCER IN BUKHARA REGION Web of Scientist: International Scientific research Journal ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 11, Nov., 2022 538-544

23. Khaidarova Nargiza Akhtamovana, PANOMORPHOLOGY OF FETUS ASPHIXIA. Web of Scientist: International Scientific research Journal. .№ 3(8) P .501-508.

24. Shodiev O'lmas Mustafoevich, Khaidarova Nargiza Akhtamovana(2022/6/19) EPITELIAL SAFE TUMORS OF BLADDER RATE,

TYPES AND CAUSES. Web of Scientist: International Scientific research Journal. № 3(6) P .905-912

25. Shodiev O'lmas Mustafoevich, Khaidarova Nargiza Akhtamovana(2022/6/19) .MEETING OF KIDNEY CYSTERS IN COURT MEDICAL AUTOPSY PRACTICE. Web of Scientist: International Scientific research Journal. № 3(6) P .893-898

26. Хайдарова Наргизахон Ахтамжон кизи Морфологические Изменения Сердца У 6-Месячных Белых Беспородных Крыс Под Влиянием Энергетического Напитка AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 1(7), 142-146.

